

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE LEADERSHIP TRAITS OF CHINGGIS KHAN AND MODERN MANAGERS"

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Abstract

"This study explores how the leadership of Chinggis Khaan, the founder of the most powerful empire in human history, has been examined within the field of management science. The study aims to identify leadership traits and skills to be learnt from him.

Keywords: Chinggis Khaan, leadership, leadership traits, frequency, comparison, results.

Introduction

Many studies have been proved the remarkable success of Chinggis Khaan achieved in a wide range of policies and actions across various fields, including politics, society, economy, trade, governance, law, justice, human rights, family and child protection, military affairs, armed forces, foreign relations, and diplomacy during establishment and strengthening the Great Mongol Empire. Based on it, it needs to clarify or study in

details of highlighted leadership traits of Chinggis Khaan compared to skills of modern managers.

"Characteristics of a Modern Leader: Situational theory suggests that effective leadership depends on the specific situation, the chosen leadership approach, and the characteristics of the followers. Over time, scholars have identified a wide range of leadership traits and skills through their research works. These are summarized in below Table 1.

Table 1.

Study findings of leadership traits and skills

Year	Scholars	
1929	A. Bowden, Prof of South California University	Hair and eye colors, voice, body height and weight are very important to become a leader (Bowden, 1929)
1935	Ordue Tead, Scholar	It is believed that a great leader can be defined by five characteristics: being energetic, courageous, friendly, sociable, and disciplined (Tead, 1935)
	Charles Bird, Prof of Minnesota University	79 traits and skills of leader have been determined in about 20 previous studies done since year of 1904 (Charles Bird)
1948	Rulp Stogdill, Prof of Ohio University, USA	32 personal characteristics of a leader have been identified through the summary of 124 similar nature studied conducted on years between 1904 and 1948 (Stogdill, 1948)
1955	R. Stogdill and S. Shartle	Stogdill and Shartle are jointly defined 10 leadership traits in year of 1955
1974	R. Stogdill	The additional traits were defined through summary of 163 studies conducted between years of 1949 and 1970 (Stogdill, 1974)
1987	G. Kausis and B. Posner	Their study presents that people are likely follow up 7 leadership traits in most cases.
1987	Keit Simonton, psychologist from USA	He said all presidents of America have had about 100 leadership characteristics and 115 characteristics owned by Napoleon Bonapart (Simonton, 1987)
1999	Brosnahan	Special attention is paid on development of particular 7 leadership traits (Brosnahan, 1999)
2001	Tom Peters	Determined 50 leadership traits and skills (Tom Peters, 2001)
2009	Warren Bennis	Mentioned about 90 traits in own study (Warren Bennis, 2009)

Among these, the version described by Stanford University Professor Tom Peters was selected for this study because it was conducted in 2001—a relatively recent timeframe. This version not only integrates the findings of previous research but also presents a broader set of leadership characteristics and skills that align more closely with the demands of modern scientific, technological, and social development. These skills can be considered as representing the essence of

effective leadership. In this respect, they offer certain advantages over the characteristics and skills proposed by Professor Warren Bennis in 2009

Tom Peters identified 50 leadership characteristics¹ and skills within the personality approach. He suggests that by grouping these traits into related categories, we can better understand the common qualities of modern leaders.

Table 2.

Common traits of Modern Leaders

	Common Traits	Meaning and Content	50 characteristics and skills of leader proposed by Tom Peters
1	Vision and Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Great idea Vision • Strategy thinking • Change management • Non sustainability management • Build networking • Trust to change the universe 	1. Vision and Strategy. 5. Leader changes the chaos into the possibility. 12. Leader manages uncertainty. 13. Leader builds the networking. 42. Leaders are confident that they can change the world.
2	Leading skills of others	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Charismatic Leadership • Accept the diversity • Build team • Build trust • Assign power • Motivation 	2. The strong admiration or devotion to a single leader is often seen as a mark of their success 9. A leader succeeds because of the support and strength of the people behind them. 10. A leader recognizes the importance of interdependence. 16. A leader relies on trust. 17. he leader holds the position as powerful representative 21. Leaders enjoy collaborating with other leaders. 27. For truly pragmatic reasons, leaders like all the colors of the rainbow. 45. Leaders willingly surround themselves with individuals who are smarter than they are. 49. A leader encourages you to think independently.
3	Personal characters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-development • Self-management • Ethics • Flexibility • Belief and trust • Intuition • Humility • Humor 	3. Leadership may be a mystery. 4. Leadership does not diminish talent 8. A leader creates himself. 11. A leader performs several tasks at the same time. 15. A leader believes in a sixth sense. 18. A leader can forget. 22. A Leader has humor senses. 25. Leaders focus on the "intangible". 41. Leaders focus on the "intangible" 46. Great leaders are also great politicians. 48. Leaders are easy learners.
4	Making decision and problem settlement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on available information • Fast • Flexible • Pragmatic • Risk responsibility • Always learn from mistakes 	20. Leaders don't repeat their mistakes. 29. True leaders never prepare for the last war." 31. Leaders promote murderers within their organizations.
5	Innovation and adaptability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open for new ideas • Use technology • Continues improvement • Promote the changes • Combining tradition with innovation. 	14. Leadership is the art for improvement. 23. Leaders like design references. 24. Leaders better knows when design should be reconsidered. 32. Leaders love the technology.
6	Communication and impacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Productive relations • Motivation • Listening skill • Persuasion 	33. Leaders radiate inspiration. 39. Leaders like the history. 40. Leaders find ways to make people go far. 43. Leaders need to talk more. 44. Leaders are a good listener.
7	Organization and management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structure and organization • Human resource management • Concentrate on outcomes • Information management • Resource management • Quality management 	6. Leaders are rarely the best performers. 7. A leader increases results. 19. Leaders involve people from all walks of life in the work. 28. True leaders are driven by purpose, not just achievements 30. Leaders must achieve results. 35. Leaders manage the communities. 38. Leadership is the performance. 47. Leaders perform meaningful work.

8	Ethics and Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Justice Respect Loyalty 	36. Leaders prefer the respect. 37. Leaders keep their word and deliver on their promises. 50. Leaders know when they leave.
9	Strength and endurance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perseverance Vigor Patience 	34. Leaders knows better that power supporting them.
10	Train in-comers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Train the incomers Sustainability 	26. Leaders always educate and train their disciples.

Source: produced by author

In addition to personal characteristics, effective leadership encompasses key qualities such as the ability to manage people and organizations, solve problems, make decisions, innovate, implement vision and strategy, prepare successors, and demonstrate ethics, commitment, and energy. This demonstrates that a modern leader must be multifaceted, possessing a diverse range of characteristics and skills, while also being well-rounded enough to effectively engage and influence every aspect of the organization.

Leadership traits of Chinggis Khaan. Many studies have been proved the remarkable success of Chinggis Khaan achieved in a wide range of policies and actions across various fields, including politics, society, economy, trade, governance, law, justice, human rights, family and child protection, military affairs, armed forces, foreign relations, and diplomacy during establishment and strengthening the Great Mongol Empire. Therefore, it is required to analyze, summarize,

and clarify the leadership qualities and skills of Chinggis Khaan based on the findings of proper studies accordingly.

Chinggis Khaan’s leadership skills, as defined by foreign scholars: The larger companies recognize that navigating globalization is the number one challenge for business leaders in the 21st century where multinational corporations operate without borders and globalization is reshaping business dynamics.

This highlights the urgent need for leaders with a Chinggis Khaan-style approach. As a result, his leadership style and skills have garnered significant attention from scholars and have been extensively studied.

Modern management science has analyzed Genghis Khan's leadership from various angles, leading to several key conclusions, which are summarized in the table below.

Table 3.

Leadership traits and skills of Chinggis Khaan as defined by foreign scholars

<u>1997 - Blenheim Partners:</u> Leadership skills and methods of Chinggis Khan ²	<u>1999 – Kim Jong Rae:</u> Leadership Techniques of Chinggis Khan ³	<u>2007 - Mike Yates:</u> 4E’s Leadership Framework of Chinggis Khan ⁴	<u>2018 - Forbes Magazine:</u> Seven lessons of Chinggis Khan from Weatherford's book ⁵
• Open-mindedness	• Practicality	• Envision – Ability to foresee	• Not to control, but to lead
• Speed and Strength	• Speed	• Enable – Ability to implement	• Care for others, not just yourself
• Building a System of Trust within the Team	• Adaptability and Strength	• Energize – Energy to achieve goals	• Be visionary
• New Ideas and Solutions	• System for Replenishing Capability	• Empower – Granting appropriate authority to subordinates	• Believe only in yourself
	• Trust Built on Sharing Hardships and Joys		• Be humble
	• Risk-Taking Attempt		• Avoid excessive luxury
			• Change the world, but do so gradually

Source: produced by author

As seen from the table, modern management scholars have thoroughly examined Chinggis Khaan's leadership process, identifying key lessons to be learned. These studies have also quantified the frequency with which Genghis Khan's leadership skills are mentioned, emphasizing the characteristics and skills that appear more than twice.

Table 4.

Leadership Traits and Skills of Chinggis Khaan Frequently Mentioned by Foreign Scholars

	Trait/Skill Studied Scholars	Blenheim Partners	Kim Jong Rae	Mick Yates	Forbes	Frequency
1	Building trust within the group	3	5	4		4→3
2	Vision	4	–	1	3	4→3
3	Caring for others	4	–	1	3	4→3
4	New ideas and solutions	–	4	2	1	4→3
5	Knowledge and skills	2	2, 3, 4	3	–	4→3
6	Speed and strength	–	5	–	2	4→3
7	Self-confidence	–	6	–	4	4→2
8	Simplicity, openness, humility	1	–	–	5, 6	4→2
9	Empowering subordinates	–	–	4	1	4→2
10	Adaptability	–	3	–	–	4→1
11	Risk-taking attempts	–	6	–	–	4→1
12	Changing the world	–	–	–	7	4→1

Source: produced by author

The table findings are represented in Figure as below:

Figure 1. Leadership Traits and Skills of Chinggis Khaan Frequently Mentioned by Foreign Scholars

Red color presents of the highest frequency, blue higher, green fair while brown shows of lowest frequency of leading traits and skills in the figure respectively.

From this, it becomes clear that the most frequently mentioned traits include: vision or goal-setting, the knowledge and skills required to achieve those goals, the ability to generate new ideas and solutions, caring for others, building trust within a team, and the speed and strength needed to accomplish these goals.

The leadership traits of Chinggis Khaan as defined by national scholars: The works of our respected scholars have contributed specific findings about Genghis Khan's leadership abilities. For example, in his book 'The Art of Leadership of Mongolian Kings and Leaders' (2009), Dr. Professor D. Lkhaashid highlighted five

key leadership traits of Genghis Khan⁶. In another example, Dr. Professor H. Purevdagva, in his work 'A Brief Guide to Genghis Khan's Management' (2004), listed nine leadership traits that developed in him up until the age of 18⁷. In addition, academician S. Naran-gerel, in 'The Ethics and Religion of Genghis Khan' (2013), outlined 28 ethical traits and behaviors that shaped him⁸. In studying the historical events mentioned in the Secret History of the Mongols, English scholar G.Batkhurel (2011) identified 37 traits and skills that he called the 'Secrets of Genghis Khan's Leadership'⁹. Likewise, academician T. Dorj, in his work 'The Secret of Genghis Khan's Leadership Wisdom' (2016), defined 10 key traits and abilities¹⁰. All of these findings are summarized in the table below

Table 5.

Characteristics and Skills of Chinggis Khaan’s Leadership Most Frequently Mentioned by National scholars

	Trait/Skill Studied Scholar	Doctor, Professor D. Lkhaashid (1999)	Doctor, Professor Kh. Purevdavga (2004)	Doctor, Professor G. Batkhurel (2011)	Academician S. Narangerel (2014)	Academician T. Dorj (2016)	Frequency
1	Wise	1	8	9	18, 20, 22, 23	5	5→5
2	Empathetic	2	4	21			5→3
3	Collaborates with others		5, 9	5	6	6	5→4
4	Flexible	4	5			7	5→3
5	Strategic foresight	5		3	18	8	5→4
6	Caring for people		2	7	2, 4, 6, 16, 17, 20, 26	2, 4	5→4
7	Resilient spirit		1		1, 10		5→2
8	Attracts others through compassion		2			10	5→2
9	Hiring the best people	3	4	14		5	5→4
10	Truthfulness			4	1, 8	2	5→3
11	Developing others		4, 7, 8	18		5	5→3

Source: produced by author

The table findings are represented in Figure as below:

Figure 2. Characteristics and skills of Chinggis Khaan's leadership most frequently mentioned by national scholars

Skills marked in red have the highest frequency, skills marked in blue have a high frequency, skills marked in green have a medium frequency, and skills marked in brown have a low frequency. Skills marked in red and blue will have the highest frequency.

In the figure: the attribute 'Wise' is the most frequently mentioned attribute in all scholars' research,

while 'Strategic thinking', 'Hiring the best', 'Caring for people', and 'Collaborating with others' are attributes with a high frequency.

Comparative results: Now, compared analysis of the leadership traits and skills of Genghis Khan, which are frequently mentioned in the research of both internal and external scholars.

Table 6.

Comparative Results of the Leadership Traits and Skills of Genghis Khan Frequently Mentioned by both foreign and National Scholars

	Research by foreign scholars	Frequency	Research by domestic scholars	Frequency
1			Intelligent	5→5
2	Building trust within the team	4→3	Collaborating with others	5→4
3	Vision	4→3	Strategic thinking	5→4
4	Caring for others	4→3	Caring for people	5→4
5	Knowledge and skills	4→3	Hiring the best people	5→4
6	New ideas, solutions	4→3		
7	Speed, strength	4→3		
8	Simplicity	4→2		
9	Empowering subordinates	4→2		
10	Self-confidence	4→2		
11			Empathetic	5→3
12			Flexible	5→3
13			Developing others	5→3
14			Truthfulness	5→3
15			Resilient spirit	5→2
16			Attracting others through compassion	5→2

Source: Produced by author

The table findings are represented in Figure as below:

Figure 3. Comparative results of the characteristics and skills of Chinggis Khaan's leadership most frequently mentioned by both foreign and National Scholars

When summarizing the characteristics and skills of Chinggis Khan's leadership most frequently mentioned in foreign and domestic scholars' research: the indicator "**Being intelligent**" appears with the highest frequency. Furthermore, the following attributes show

both high frequency and overlap between the two groups:

- **Visionary thinking** (or strategic foresight)
- **Knowledge and competence, new ideas and solutions** (or recruiting the best talent)

- **Caring for others** (or valuing people)
- **Building trust within the team** (or cooperating with others).

From these results, it can be observed that both foreign and domestic scholars generally emphasize, alongside vision and goals, the importance of intellectual (IQ) attributes such as the knowledge, skills, and innovative solutions needed to achieve them. In addition, they highlight emotional (EQ) attributes such as caring for others, collaborating, and building trust within teams, which also show high frequency and

overlap. This indicates that emotional intelligence or spirituality in the workplace was a predominant aspect of Chinggis Khan's leadership. Thus, it is reasonable to conclude that Chinggis Khan was a leader of great intellect and spirit.

Comparative analysis on leadership traits and skills of modern leaders and Chinggis Khaan. At the conclusion of this article, we will compare the leadership characteristics of Genghis Khan, as identified by scholarly research, with those of modern leaders, aiming to clarify the extent to which they align."

Table 7.

Comparative analysis results

	Common characteristics of Modern leaders (by Tom Peters)	Leadership traits of Chinggis Khaan defined by scholars	Concurrence
1	Personal characters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wise • Sensitive • Open-minded • Flexible • Humility • Simple 	•
2	Vison and Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vision -long-term policy 	•
3	Managing skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperating with others -build trust among colleagues 	•
4	Communication and impacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caring for others – love others • Attracting others through kindness 	•
5	Innovation and adaptability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New ideas and solution • Hire the best one-knowledge and competence 	•
7	Managing the organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop out others and assign power to low level people 	•
	Making decision -problem solving	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self- trust 	•
8	Ethics and Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To be honest 	•
9	Strength and endurance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Speed and power • Patience 	•
10	Train the incomers		

Source: Produced by author

As the table shows, Chinggis Khaan's leadership traits align approximately 90% with those of modern leaders.

Conclusion: The findings indicate that the leadership traits of Chinggis Khaan, a leader from over 800 years ago, are largely consistent with those of contemporary leaders.

Additionally, the characteristics of a leader in a nomadic civilization are fundamentally similar to those of a leader in a settled civilization. This situation:

- Demonstrates that Chinggis Khaan was a leader capable of adapting to any era or lifestyle, meeting the management and societal needs of his time.
- Shows that true leadership transcends time and lifestyle, depending instead on the leader's mindset and level of development.

Chinggis Khaan possessed a diverse range of leadership skills: he was not only intelligent, sensitive, disciplined, energetic, resilient, open, flexible, simple, and humble, but also a visionary leader who successfully implemented his grand strategy. He achieved this by continuously training, empowering, and developing himself, his followers, his team, and his nation.

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